

Enhancing Charge Transport in Perovskite Solar Cell: Achieving Over 85.5% Fill Factor by Introducing [1]benzothieno[3,2-*b*][1] benzothiophene Derivative Interlayer

Daimiota Takhellambam¹, Luigi Angelo Castriotta¹, Gloria Zanotti², Laura Mancini², Venanzio Raglione², Giuseppe Mattioli², Barbara Paci³, Amanda Generosi³, Marco Guaragno³, Valerio Campanari³, Giuseppe Ammirati^{1,3}, Faustino Martelli⁴, Emanuele Calabrò¹, Narges Yaghoobi Nia^{5,6}, Francesco Di Giacomo¹, Aldo Di Carlo^{1,3}*

¹Center for Hybrid and Organic Solar Energy (CHOSE), Department of Electronics Engineering, University of Rome ‘Tor Vergata’, Viale Pietro Gismondi - Casale 11 -, 00133, Roma, Italy,

E-mail: aldo.dicarlo@uniroma2.it

²G. Zanotti, L. Mancini, V. Raglione, G. Mattioli

Istituto di Struttura della Materia (ISM) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche(CNR), via Salaria km 29.300 Monterotondo, 00015, Roma, Italy

³B. Paci, A. Generosi, M. Guaragno, V. Campanari, G. Ammirati, A. Di Carlo

Istituto di Struttura della Materia- Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche Roma (ISM-CNR), via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, Rome 00133, Italy

⁴F. Martelli

Istituto per la Microelettronica e i Microsistemi - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche Roma (ISM-CNR), via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, Rome 00133, Italy

^{5,6} N. Yaghoobi Nia

Department of Electronics Engineering, University of Rome Tor Vergata, Via del Politecnico 1, 00133 Roma, Italy.

School of Aerospace Engineering, University of Rome “La Sapienza”, Via Salaria, 851 – 00138 Rome, Italy.

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Perovskite solar cells have received considerable attention for their increasing photovoltaic performance achieved through fine optimization of stacking layers and experimentation with device architecture. The incorporation of interlayers has been shown to positively impact the fabrication process by improving photovoltaic parameters. In recent years, carbazole-based Self-Assembled Monolayers (SAMs) have been investigated as a potential Hole Transport Layer (HTL), due to their efficient passivating nature at the hole selective interface and faster charge extraction. This study introduces a novel interlayer 2-decyl[1]benzothieno [3,2-*b*][1]benzothiophene (C10-BTBT), over the HTL self-assembled monolayer (2-(3,6-Dimethoxy-9H-carbazol-9-yl) ethyl) phosphonic acid, also known as MeO-2PACz. This new interlayer over SAMs significantly improves charge transfer at the interface, resulting in a high fill factor of 85.89% and a boost in power conversion efficiency from 18.04% to 20.50%. This research highlights the potential of interlayer-SAM combinations in advancing perovskite solar cell technology.

1. Introduction

Perovskites have gained significant attention as active photovoltaic materials due to rapid increase of PSC efficiency. In 2009, Perovskites Solar Cells (PSCs) demonstrated a Power Conversion Efficiency (PCE) of 3.8%, which has since escalated to 25.7% in standard architecture (n-i-p cells) and 25.49% in inverted architecture (p-i-n configuration) in just over a decade.^[1-3] The perovskite layer, which is the active absorber layer, has been the subject of top-notch research exploring composition, concentration, defect tolerance, thickness, and crystal quality to make PSCs a promising green energy source.^[4-6] Various innovative approaches have been investigated to improve perovskite quality by using excess precursors, additives, or passivating agents.^[7-12] These strategies can be combined together to develop an universal multi-additive approach in perovskite ink as we have shown recently by combining alkylamine ligands oleylamine (OAm), ionic liquids (IL) 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (BMIM-BF₄), and benzylhydrazine hydrochloride (BHC) to improve the photovoltaic performance as well as boost the stability of p-i-n PSCs.^[13] PSCs' behavior is very related to the interface properties^[14] and high performing devices have been achieved by modifying the interfacial region.^[15-17] In a typical PSC architecture, junction interfaces are

barely the perovskite/HTL(hole transport layer) and the perovskite/ETL(electron transport layer) junctions. Owing to the role Fill Factor (FF) has on the efficiency of the cell, the improvement in charge transport with a modification in the junction layer is the key factor in realizing a high FF and improved J_{sc} .^[18–20] Among the several solutions proposed for interface engineering, a key strategy based on Self Assembled Monolayers (SAMs) has been considered for p-i-n PSCs as hole selective junction layer.^[21] Interface engineering with SAM permits to tune the workfunction of the underlayer thus improving the charge transfer and also the crystallization of the perovskite.^[22] From the large library of SAMs as HTL, the carbazole derivative MeO-2PACz, a modified version of 2-PACz,^[23] shows excellent hole transporting ability owing to electron localizing property in the core molecule.^[24] Use of MeO-2PACz proved the benefits of ease in preparation, deposition, and conformal coverage.^[23] In fact, the presence of phosphonic acid in MeO-2PACz makes it a simple molecule to adhere stably and strongly on the surface of Indium Tin Oxide (ITO).

In the present work we focus on a small organic molecule [1]benzothieno[3,2-b][1]benzothiophene (BTBT) as an effective interlayer between the SAM and halide perovskite absorber. BTBT has been a state of the art material in organic electronics for several years now, especially in the field of Organic Field-Effect Transistors (OFETs), Organic Thin Film Transistors (OTFTs), and more recently, Luminescent Solar Concentrators (LSCs).^[25] This is mainly due to the fused rigid and planar π -system of the BTBT molecule that promotes charge carrier delocalization and intermolecular interactions, a high chemical stability due to their low lying highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), a fine modulation of their chemical and electronic properties via straightforward functionalization of the aromatic thienoacene core, and easily accessible synthetic protocols.^[26,27] Among the best-performing derivatives, alkylated BTBTs have demonstrated hole mobilities^[28,29] higher than $1.0 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which are largely dependent on the herringbone packing of the films, modulated by the alkyl chains, and further aided by strong intermolecular overlaps promoted by sulfur-sulfur interactions induced by the zipper effect, beneficial for an effective charge transport. Despite their superior hole transport properties, air stability, and easy processability, only a few implementations of BTBT derivatives in new-generation photovoltaics have been reported in the literature so far.^[30,31]

Figure 1. (A) Synthesis of C10-BTBT (a) decanoyl chloride, aluminum trichloride (AlCl_3), anhydrous dichloromethane (DCM), $-80^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow \text{rt}$; (b) sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), AlCl_3 , anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (THF), $-10^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow 66^\circ\text{C}$ (B) Molecular structure of MeO-2PACz (C) Equilibrium geometry of a MeOPACz/C10-BTBT dyad, calculated using DFT simulations (D) Schematic representation of planar p-i-n architecture of C10-BTBT modified PSC

Herein, we report the use of the small organic molecule 2-Decyl-[1]benzothieno[3,2-*b*][1]benzothiophene (C10-BTBT) mono alkylated with a carbon linear straight-chain for interface engineering in our PSCs. The use of highly crystalline C10-BTBT over MeO-2PACz efficiently helps extract the charge carriers to the perovskite/HTL interface, supported by theoretical simulation showing a tendency of cofacial interaction between them. The use of the interlayer does not induce any morphological or crystal structure change in the perovskite layer. Our demonstration of interfacial engineering with the use of an organic small molecule with high hole mobility in low temperature processed PSCs opens up a gateway for making C10-BTBT a general thin film interfacial layer that can be utilized in different architectures of existing PSCs. Consequent of the utilization of C10-BTBT as interlayer, we could achieve an ultra-high fill factor of 85.89% and an absolute boost in the overall photovoltaic parameter with a leap of $\sim 2.5\%$ (2% on average) power conversion efficiency. We attained PCE of 20.5% on an active area of 0.09 cm^2 and tested the durability of the cells (ISOSL1) under 1 SUN illumination and realized T_{80} of 803 hours in air without proper encapsulation and environmental stability (ISOS D1) T_{80} of more than 1608 hours.

Table 1. Optoelectrochemical and theoretical characterization of C10-BTBT^[28] and MeO-2PACz^[23], given versus vacuum and simulations of voltammetric measurements in CH₂Cl₂

	E _{ox} (eV)		E _{red} (eV)		E _g (eV)	
	exp	theo	exp	theo	opt	theo
C10-BTBT	-5.5	-5.46	-2.0	-1.73	3.5	3.73
MeO-2PACz	-5.3	-5.11	-2.1	-1.64	3.2	3.47

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 C10-BTBT details:

The synthesis of C10-BTBT was carried out following a published two-step procedure.^[32] The synthesis scheme followed is sketched in **Figure 1A**, using BTBT as a starting material. Detailed experimental protocols can be found in the experimental section. Briefly, benzothienobenzothiophene core was functionalized with decanoyl chloride using a conventional Friedel-Crafts acylation protocol. The carbonyl group was then reduced with sodium borohydride and aluminum chloride in anhydrous THF to afford the target product. The ¹H NMR of the acylated intermediate and of the final compound in Figure S1 and S2 are in agreement with the expected structure both in the alkyl and aromatic proton regions. Thanks to its decyl chain, C10-BTBT is soluble in the most common organic solvents. The optical, electrochemical and computational characterization of C10-BTBT is summarized in Table 1 along with MeO-2PACz (molecular structure in Figure 2B). The optical response of the molecule Figure S3 lies in the ultraviolet region, with the S₀-S₁ transition peaked at 330 nm. The cyclovoltammetric parameters are taken from the literature^[4] and confirm the high band-gap nature of C10-BTBT, whose oxidation potential lies at 5.5 eV, in close agreement with the theoretical simulations of the two molecules in CH₂Cl₂ solution.

In addition, to separate C10-BTBT and MeO-2PACz molecules, we have theoretically investigated their interaction starting with a C10-BTBT/MeO-2PACz dyad studied at DFT level (see details in S.I.). As shown in Figure 1C, the two molecules exhibit a tendency to the cofacial interaction of the carbazole and benzothiophene planes, with an interaction energy of 0.65 eV. Such interaction preserves the correct alignment of electronic levels, with excess holes localized on MeO-2PACz rather than on C10-BTBT, as detailed in Figure S4 and Table S1, with an even slight advantage (0.1 eV) in the collection of holes for MeO-2PACz molecules when associated with C10-BTBT. Moreover, theoretical results suggest that C10-BTBT can have a twofold electronic and structural role in the formation of the interfacial layer between perovskite and

ITO, helping the SAM to collect more efficiently the incoming charge carriers. Indeed, large scale tight-binding simulations indicate that 1:1 C10-BTBT/MeO-2PACz blends have a stronger tendency to intermixing rather than segregation of the two parts, with the preferential formations of cofacial C10-BTBT/MeO-2PACz pairs and the total lack of direct cofacial interaction between BTBT molecules (Figure S5a), which is generally the main feature of alkylated BTBT crystals.^[33] Finally, such structural results obtained in blends are confirmed after 1ns of molecular dynamics simulation starting with a monolayer of C10-BTBT placed on top of a free-standing monolayer of tightly packed MeO-2PACz (density around $1.5 \cdot 10^{14}$ molecules per cm^2) and ending with C10-BTBT completely incorporated and dispersed into the MeO-2PACz layer (Figure S5b).

2.2 Device Optimization and Morphology

We used a triple cation perovskite (3C-Pvk) as active layer and carried out various characterizations to investigate the influence of monoalkylated C10-BTBT as interlayer. Our device structure is ITO/MeO-2PACz/(w/wo) C10-BTBT/3C-Pvk/PC₆₁BM/BCP/Cu. We used [6,6] phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PC₆₁BM), Bathocuproine (BCP) on top of perovskite and copper (Cu) as the charge collection electrode. A detailed procedure for the preparation of perovskite precursors is given in the experimental section. We adopted a device architecture to use C10-BTBT as interlayer because of its sole use as HTL yielded a maximum of PCE of 9.8%. Figure S6 sums up the J-V plot and statistics of deploying C10-BTBT as HTL.

In various dissolution trials, we fixed dimethylformamide (DMF) to be the solvent of our choice to dissolve C10-BTBT and optimization of concentration is represented in Figure S7 where we found 0.5 mgml^{-1} in DMF to be the most effective concentration. The reason for choosing DMF as compared to other polar solvents such as chlorobenzene, toluene, and dichloromethane is two-fold. First, it took an hour to homogeneously dissolve C10-BTBT in DMF. This is a plus point considering that we use an ultrathin MeO-2PACz SAM as our HTL. Solvents that dissolve both the HTL and the interlayer are omitted, as the process may lead to removal of the previous deposited layer which is already annealed. Second, there are reports on the use of DMF solvent as a wetting material before deposition of perovskite and increase the perovskite coverage and performance of a cell.^[34] The coverage of perovskite is indeed better, but we did not see much impact, see Figure S8, in the overall improvement of photovoltaic performance in solely using DMF without the use of C10-BTBT as interlayer.

Figure 2. (A) UV-vis spectra of the perovskite films grown on top of ITO/MeO₂PACz/ with C10-BTBT or without (control); (B) Top view Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of perovskite grown on ITO/MeO-2PACz; (C) AFM image panels of control surface 30 x 30 μm^2 ; (D) Tauc plot from the corresponding UV-vis spectra; (E) SEM image of perovskite grown on ITO/MeO₂PACz/C10-BTBT; (F) AFM image panels of modified surface 30 x 30 μm^2 ; (G-H) Fabricated device cross sectional SEM image (control - G) and (with interfacial layers - H); (I) Comparison of r.m.s. evolution in the different intermediate perovskite layers as deduced from AFM images of different dimensions

Therefore, any further characterization has been carried out with the optimized concentration of the interlayer until the end. Initially, we characterized UV-vis absorption of both perovskite films grown on MeO-2PACz and to observe the influence of interlayer with C10-BTBT on top. Figure 2A illustrates a comparison of the control (without C10-BTBT) and modified devices (with C10-BTBT) showing comparable light absorption profiles, that hints there is no significant change in the spectra as well as the perovskite bandgap energy (1.64eV) as represented in Figure 2D. This entails that the use of interlayer C10-BTBT induces no major

modification in the perovskite bulk. To further support this observation, we perform analyses of the surface morphology of the perovskite films deposited on MeO₂PACz and C10-BTBT by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) reported in Figure 2B and 2E, respectively which shows an uniform surface and a good crystallinity. We could not observe any pin-hole formation even on a larger area capture confirmed by SEM in Figure S9. In this morphological comparison of control and modified devices, there is no distinct difference on the crystal quality and distribution across the surface. This ensures us that the use of C10-BTBT induces no change in the perovskite quality or shape which is also evident from the cross-section SEM images Figure 2G and 2H. Further investigation of the surface by means of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is performed on several portions of each perovskite film in order to obtain statistically relevant information on the morphology. The following are representative of the surface texture, showing in different panels images of Figure 2C and 2F (30x30) μm^2 (see 20x20 μm^2 and 10x10 μm^2 in Figure S10). The statistical analysis performed upon the specified images evaluates the homogeneity of the perovskite surface texture, and the results are reported in Figure 2I. As visible, independently of the presence of C10-BTBT as underlayer, the perovskite texture is always homogeneous with small globular structures being observed, and roughness is comparable throughout. The analysis shows us the minimal difference of the root mean square roughness (RMS) values and further confirm that there is little difference with the use of interlayer.

Diving further, in-depth analysis of the effect of stacked layers on depositing perovskite on top is checked with X-ray diffraction (XRD). The quality of the perovskite crystal formation is represented in Figure 3A. Perovskite films exhibit a cubic polycrystalline-phase (space group $\text{Pm}\bar{3}\text{m}$) with Miller indexes attributed to each reflection accordingly to literature.^[35,36] Our samples showed the presence of almost negligible spurious crystalline (002) PbI_2 (JCDD card nr: 01-073-175). The comparison of XRD patterns obtained from both films with and without interlayer suggests us that the crystal quality remains unchanged and there is no effect induced in the perovskite with the use of C10-BTBT as interlayer. High crystallinity results from XRD analysis shows us that there is minimal trap density at the interface between C10-BTBT/perovskite. The fact itself that no major changes are induced on to the perovskite opens up a variety of possibilities in several device structures and to look forward to a better performing device by introducing C10-BTBT as an interlayer.

Figure 3. (A) XRD image collected at high angle comparing control and modified device until the perovskite layer; (B) High angle XRD image comparing device with and without PC₆₁BM deposition on top of perovskite layer (Inset- new hydrated perovskite complex peak); (C) Steady state photoluminescence spectra (PL) of control and modified device; (D) Time resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) spectra

We further investigate the impact of the C10-BTBT on the other layers deposited on top of perovskite layer. XRD results reported in Figure 3B show us that with the use of solution prepared ETLs PC₆₁BM in our device fabrication, we detect a negligible peak indicating a perovskite complex. XRD patterns comparing the GLASS/ ITO/ MeO/ interlayer/ Pvk versus GLASS/ ITO/ MeO/ interlayer/ Pvk/ PC₆₁BM are reported. Perovskite crystalline structure is perfectly preserved and labeled as previously discussed. As it is visible, no crystalline signature could be attributed to the fullerene layer. Furthermore, as highlighted in the inset of Figure 3B, when the PCBM film is grown on top of the perovskite, the appearance of hydrated perovskite

complexes is observed. Indeed, the signature at $2\theta = 11.35^\circ$ is the fingerprint of $\text{MAPbI}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.^[37] Low angular XRD is performed to observe the possible formation of 2D structures in order to monitor the effect of C10-BTBT on the perovskite structure, however no such feature revealed (Figure S11A).

XRD analysis was also applied to the complete cell up to the metal electrode (copper) to see the rise of additional peaks (Figure S11 B). All contributions previously discussed are still detected and no crystalline signature attributed to bathocuproine (BCP) is observed due to small thickness or deposition process resulting in non-crystalline film. The copper electrode signature [JCDD card nr: 00-003-1005, Crystal system: Cubic, Space group: Fm3m, Space group number: 225] in the complete cell is not visible, due to the fact that Cu signal is masked from the overlapping perovskite and ITO reflections as reported in (Figure S11 B).

We also investigated the steady state and time-resolved photoluminescence in complete cells ITO/HTL/(w/wo)C10-BTBT/3C-Pvk/ETL/Cu, the steady state photoluminescence (PL) intensity of the modified device is slightly weaker than that of the control sample while the lineshape shows a reduced full width at half maximum in the modified device (Figure 3C). These small changes are comparable with the typical PL inhomogeneity observed for perovskites.^[38,39] These features are further indication of the maintenance of the perovskite physical properties in the modified devices as well as the the position of the PL peak that is for both films is at 755 nm. Hence, the PL confirms what already observed by optical absorption and XRD, namely that no significant change is observed in the material properties with the introduction of the new molecule in the active absorber bulk. The decay time of the time resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) intensity are shown in Figure 3D. The decay dynamics are very similar for control and modified samples. Table S1 sums up all fitting parameters of the TRPL curves. The decay of the PL intensity can be fitted with a biexponential curve. The shorter lifetimes τ_1 , which represents non radiative recombination, slightly decreased from 4.0 ns (control) to 3.4 ns (modified) in half structure HTL/(w/wo C10-BTBT)/3C-Pvk, while it remained equal (2.1 ns) in both full structure HTL/(w/wo C10-BTBT)/3C-Pvk/ETL/Cu. Also the longer lifetime τ_2 , which approximately corresponds to the electron-hole recombination time, is not affected in significant ways. It decreased from 28.0 ns (control) to 21.0 ns (modified) for the half device and slight increased from 10.5 ns (control) to 12.7 ns (modified) for the full device. Given the well-known fluctuation of these values in perovskites, these

values confirm that no significant change of the physical properties of the active layer occurs when the C10-BTBT interlayer is added to the structure.

Table 2. Photovoltaic parameters of J-V scans under 1 SUN illumination.

Device		Voc (V)	Jsc (mAcm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Control	Best	1.10	20.20	81.25	18.04
	Average(30)	1.06 ± 0.03	20.14 ± 0.34	81.16 ± 0.54	17.57 ± 0.445
Modified	Best	1.12	21.30	85.89	20.51
	Average(30)	1.10 ± 0.02	21.10 ± 0.14	84.75 ± 0.53	20.05 ± 0.30

2.3 Photovoltaic performance

In the fabrication of *p-i-n* devices, we used the triple cation perovskite composition Cs_{0.05}MA_{0.15}FA_{0.8}PbI_{2.49}Br_{0.51} as the photoactive absorber material. The perovskite film thickness is ~ 490 nm and cross-sectional SEM images of different layers stacked in PSC are shown in Figure 2G and 2H. The cross-sectional image indicates that the multilayers deposited as a part of fabricating a complete device are well connected with defined interfaces. We used solution processed spin cast method for all the layers and evaporated Cu thermally. Details of the fabrication procedure are detailed in experimental section. As mentioned earlier, in perovskite solution processing we used our reported procedure of the additives^[40] where we used IL, OAm, and BHH few minutes before the deposition. We show the J-V curves in Figure 4A and the corresponding summarized photovoltaic parameters are listed in Table 2. The highest PCE of the control devices recorded from the reverse(forward) J-V scan is 18.01 (18.04)%, with a Jsc (Short Circuit Current Density) value of 20.23 (20.15) mAcm⁻², Voc(Open Circuit Voltage) value of 1.10 (1.10)V, and FF (Fill factor) 80.60 (81.25) %. On the other hand, with the interlayer, the performance increased up to PCE=20.51 (19.73)%, with Jsc=21.32 (21.26) mAcm⁻², Voc =1.12 (1.12)V and FF= 85.89 (82.99)% from the reverse (forward) J-V scan. Figure 4B shows the related external quantum efficiency (EQE) and the corresponding integrated photocurrent. The detailed comparison of the photovoltaic device parameters is presented in Table 2 by taking a performance mean of 30 cells. The hysteresis index (HI) calculated for the champion cells of control and interlayer modified devices are 0.16% and 3.80% respectively, however, if we look at other C10-BTBT modified devices, HI is much

Figure 4. (A) J-V curve of control and modified devices; (B) External quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra for both control and modified best device; (C) Box plot of reproducibility devices of both control and modified; (D) Temporal decay of the photoluminescence intensity

reduced and for some samples showed very small to nil as represented in Figure S12. As it is evident from the photovoltaic values, there is a large 2.5% (2% on average) increase of PCE that can be attributed to the overall increase of the photovoltaic parameters and significantly of the fill factor (85.89%) which we can label as one of the highest values achieved in low temperature processed *p-i-n* PSCs using an interlayer between HTL and perovskite. Clearly the EQE spectra with the integrated current density shown in Figure 4B shows higher performance with the use of C10-BTBT than in the control device over the entire wavelength range. Considering that the absorption is similar in the two devices (Figure 2A), we argue that the increase in the short circuit current can be ascribed to a more efficient charge transfer at the

interface.^[41,42] To support this conclusion we make use of a novel technique we developed recently^[39] where we have shown that the quenching of the PL intensity, observed when switching the solar cell from open circuit (OC) to short circuit (SC), is a good indicator of the energy conversion efficiency. The PL quenching is defined as $PLQ_{oc-sc} = \frac{PL_{oc} - PL_{sc}}{PL_{oc}}$, where PL_{oc} and PL_{sc} are the PL intensity at OC and SC, respectively. The analysis of PLQ_{oc-sc} allows the evaluation of the characteristic time (τ_e) for the carrier extraction from the cell in units of the lifetime (τ_1) of the photoexcited carriers in OC conditions, which approximately corresponds to the PL lifetime. For our samples, the modified PSCs show an average PL quenching that is higher than that of the control devices (Figure S13).

Figure 5. (A-B) Contact angle measurement with perovskite solution on (A) MeO-2PACz (control) and (B) C10-BTBT (modified) surface; (C) Maximum power point tracking of the control and modified device under 1 Sun Illumination in air; (E) Environmental stability test of Control and C10-BTBT modified device

In Figure 4D, we report the τ_e/τ_1 extracted from PLQ_{oc-sc} as a function of the device efficiency for representative control and modified devices as well as the average values. The analysis of the present data with the model^[39] shows that the average value of τ_e/τ_1 decreases from 0.68 for the control devices to 0.23 for the modified devices. As the material properties do not change by inserting the interlayer, we can assume that τ_1 is very similar in the two devices. This result confirms that the carrier extraction in the modified devices is more efficient than in the control ones. This can be explained by a more efficient band alignment in the modified devices with respect to the control devices as obtained with DFT calculations. We conclude that at the end of these photophysical studies, fully supported by atomistic simulations, introducing mono alkylated C10-BTBT helps in better extraction of the charges on top of MeO-2PACz without

affecting the absorber or active layer which eventually leads to a high FF% and thus improves the photovoltaic performance.

We also investigated this potentiality in improvement to indoor light performance and achieved PCE of 33.21% efficiency at 1000 lux intensity. This suggests us that our device is a good candidate for indoor photovoltaics as well. Figure S14 and Table S3 show the J-V at different light intensities and the summary of all the parameters for indoor photovoltaic performances, respectively.

We concluded our investigation by conducting stability measurements of the devices. Figure 5A and 5B gives us the surface tension of water on top of MeO-2PACz and C10-BTBT modified surfaces, where the contact angle for control device is 45.5° and for modified device is 65.9° . The increased hydrophobicity of the interlayer modified surface is speculated to promote more stable devices and hints better protection from moisture infiltration into the perovskite layer. Contact angle measurement after 5 minutes of deposition as shown in Figure 5A and 5B shows consistent results. The cell stability test ISOS-L1, as represented in Figure 5C, is a result of constant exposure under 1 SUN illumination and we could realize T_{80} (time consumed in 20% decrease of the initial efficiency) of 345 hours for the control device and T_{80} of 803 hours for the modified device. We observe the improvement thanks to the use of interlayer C10-BTBT, indicating a more robust perovskite film against extrinsic degradation factors. Here we did not encapsulate the device, except for applying a plastic adhesive tape Kapton on top after complete fabrication of the device. Environmental stability ISOS-D1 of the control and modified device shown in Figure 5D also showed excellent stability T_{80} of 1608 hours (modified device) without proper encapsulation of the device.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we have successfully demonstrated an effective way to interfacial engineering in order to fabricate more efficient and stable perovskite solar cells. We have realized that the core use of inserting small organic molecule C10-BTBT as interlayer between the HTL MeO-2PACz and the 3C-perovskite in *p-i-n* architecture is an effective auxiliary in extracting the charges from the perovskite to the HTL thus obtaining a very high fill factor of 85.89% and ultimately an increase on the PCE increase from 18.04% to 20.5%. We have understood that our modification does not induce any changes to the layers involved in fabricating a PSCs but that the main effect is to improve the charge extraction. This conclusion is fully supported by

both experiments and DFT calculations. We view this as a new and practical technology of interlayer insertion compatible with many forms of PSCs architectures, which can further improve perovskite photovoltaics.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Methylammonium bromide (MABr>99.99%) and Formamidinium iodide (FAI>99.99%) were purchased from Greatcell solar. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-anhydrous), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF-anhydrous), toluene, chlorobenzene(CB), 1,4-dichlorobenzene(DCB), Cesium iodide (CsI-99.99%), Bathocuproine (BCP-96%), Methoxy Ethanol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. C₆₀ Fullerene (C₆₀-99.50%) and PCBM (99.50%) were purchased from Solenne. Lead Iodide (PbI₂) and Lead Bromide (PbBr₂), were purchased from TCI chemicals. Glass/ITO substrates (10 Ω sq⁻¹) were purchased from Kintec. All reagents and solvents for C10-BTBT chemical synthesis were purchased from Merck Life Science, TCI Chemicals, and Carlo Erba Reagents. All the chemicals unless stated are used directly without further purification.

Perovskite solution: 3C perovskite with composition Cs_{0.05}MA_{0.15}FA_{0.8}PbI_{2.49}Br_{0.51} with a concentration of 1.38 M was prepared by mixing CsI (17.56 mg, 0.05 mM), MABr (23.75 mg, 0.15 mM), FAI (187.92 mg, 0.8 mM), PbI₂ (532.86 mg, 0.82 mM, ~2% excess), PbBr₂ (91.47 mg, 0.18 mM) in 1 ml of a 4:1 DMF:DMSO mixture (by volume ratio) and stirred overnight.

Additive preparation: Separate stock solutions of 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (BMIM-BF₄) 50μl in 1 mL of DMF, Oleylamine (OAm) 50μl in 1mL of DMF, and 50 mg benzylhydrazine hydrochloride (BHC) in 1 ml DMF were stirred for 30 minutes. Later from the prepared stock solutions, 20μl BMIM-BF₄, 10μl OAm and 12μl benzylhydrazine hydrochloride (BHC) from the stock solutions were added per 1mL of perovskite solution 30 minutes prior perovskite deposition and kept stirred.

Synthesis of C₉H₁₉CO-BTBT: BTBT (4.00 g, 16.64 mmol) is dissolved in 160 mL of anhydrous dichloromethane in a dry 500 ml three-neck flask. The mixture is cooled to -10°C and aluminum chloride (5.60 g, 42.00 mmol) is added to it in portions. After stirring for ten minutes, the mixture is further cooled down to -83°C and decanoyl chloride (2.79 mL, 16.67 mmol) is added dropwise. After one hour, the temperature is slowly raised up to RT and the reaction is carried out overnight. The mixture is then poured in a cold 1:1 water-methanol mixture, the resulting pale-yellow solid is collected by filtration and crystallized with toluene. 5.00 g (76%). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.55 (s, 1H), 8.06 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.97 – 7.91 (m, 3H), 7.47 (dt, *J* = 15.1, 7.0 Hz, 2H), 3.07 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.84 – 1.75 (m, 2H), 1.46 – 1.22 (m, 12H), 0.89 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 3H).

Synthesis of C₁₀-BTBT: In a dry two-neck round bottom flask (500 ml) equipped with a bubble condenser, C₉H₁₉CO-BTBT (5.30 g, 13.43 mmol) is dissolved in 94 mL of anhydrous THF. The mixture is cooled to -10°C, then AlCl₃ (8.95 g, 67.15 mmol) and NaBH₄ (5.08 g, 134.3 mmol) are carefully added. After 15-20 minutes the mixture is heated to reflux and allowed to react overnight. The mixture is then cooled to room temperature and a 3:1 water/methanol mixture (150 ml) is slowly added, while cooling the flask with an ice bath. A white precipitate is formed -along with harsh bubbling-, collected by filtration, dissolved in 130 mL of propan-2-ol and hot-filtered to remove some white solid residues. 3.40 g (66%). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.88 (dd, *J* = 26.8, 7.8 Hz, 2H), 7.78 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.72 (s, 1H), 7.45 (td, *J* = 7.6, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 7.38 (td, *J* = 8.2, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.28 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 2.79 – 2.73 (m, 2H), 1.73 – 1.66 (m, 2H), 1.41 – 1.21 (m, 14H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 3H). UV-vis (dichloromethane): λ_{abs} 330, 310, 267, 239 nm.

All the reactions were performed under argon atmosphere and monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) employing a polyester layer coated with 250 mm F254 silica gel.

C10-BTBT solution: 0.5mg of C10-BTBT were dissolved in 1mL of DMF in a vial and stirred for few hours before the deposition inside nitrogen atmosphere.

Device fabrication: Glass/ITO samples were patterned with a UV ns laser (Spectra physics - Andover, MA, USA) and cut into $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ a glass cutter (Dyenamo – Stockholm, Sweden). Samples were soft scrubbed clean with water and soap solution (Hellmanex 1% in deionized water) and sonicated through three stages of ultrasonic bath: first in water and soap for 15 minutes, then in ultrapure water for 15 minutes, continued in acetone for 15 minutes and finally in Isopropyl alcohol (IPA) for 15 minutes. After drying with pressurized air gun, the glass substrates were treated with UV-O₃ (Novasonic) for 15 min. The samples were then immediately transferred to a nitrogen-filled glovebox. 150 μ L of MeO-2PACz (0.33 mgmL⁻¹ in Methoxy Ethanol) were first dropped onto the cleaned glass substrate to cover all area. After 3s, the solution was spun at 4000 rpm for 20 s and annealed for 10 min at 100 °C. After cooling down, the perovskite ink (filtered through 0.45 μ m PVDF) was spun at 4000 rpm for 35s, and 150 μ L of CB were dropped after 20 s. The film was annealed for 10 min at 100 °C. After cooling down, on top of the perovskite layer we spin casted of PC₆₁BM (27 mgmL⁻¹ in CB:DCB - 3:1 volume ratio) 80 μ L dynamically at 1600 rpm for 35s and annealed for 5 minutes at 100°C. 80 μ l of BCP (0.5 mgml⁻¹ in IPA stirred over 2 nights) was spun right after PBCM process at 3000 rpm for 30s without any further drying. 40nm C₆₀ and 8nm BCP are thermally evaporated for the light soaking devices at a vacuum pressure of ≈ 10 to 6 mbar. Finally, 100 nm of Cu were deposited by thermal evaporation, using a shadow mask.

Device characterization: Current density- Voltage J-V curves were obtained with ABET Sun 2000 class A simulator, calibrated with an Eko MS-602 pyranometer for AM 1.5G SUN

illumination. The accuracy of the calibration was checked by measuring the EQE (Arkeo system from Cicci Research, Grosseto, Italy), ensuring that the mismatch of the integrated and measured J_{SC} was less than 2%. TPV tests were performed with ARKEO which composed of multichannel 4-wire source meters, 100 MS/s digitizer, and Arbitrary function generators. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) experiments were performed by using a TESCAN Analytics VEGA instrument. UV-vis absorption of perovskite films were recorded with a Shimadzu 2600 series spectrophotometer. A Panalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer was used to perform diffraction measurements (XRD) in Bragg-Brentano configuration with Cu-anode X-ray tube (K-Alpha1 [\AA] = 1,54060; K-Alpha2 [\AA] = 1,54443) as source. Detection was accomplished by means of a PixCel 3D detector working in linear mode. The AFM images were taken using in house developed Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) mounting a $30\mu\text{m} \times 30\mu\text{m}$ scanner to determine morphological surface characteristics of the intermediate samples composing the complete cells under investigation. Non-contact mode acquisitions were collected upon several portions of each film by means of aluminum coated standard tapping AFM probes (Nanosensors), combining high operation stability with outstanding sensitivity and fast scanning ability. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE 600 NMR spectrometer operating at a proton frequency of 600.13 MHz in CDCl_3 ; chemical shifts (δ) are given in ppm relative to TMS. UV-vis spectra for C10- BTBT in dichloromethane were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 UV-vis/NIR spectrophotometer. The PL measurements were performed by exciting the samples with a 405 nm cw laser diode. The luminescence was detected with a Peltier-cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) camera after having been dispersed in a 30 cm long monochromator with a 1200 grooves/mm grating. The time-resolved PL measurements were performed with a time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) system with a photomultiplier as the detector with an instrumental response function (IRF) of 0.5 ns. The measurements were performed using a pulsed laser source (duration 40 fs)

at 380 nm with 1 KHz repetition rate for pump peak energy 300pJ. Contact angle measurement of the perovskite solution were captured with camera and evaluated with software imageJ.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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